

Instructions de montage:

- Opérer sur une surface plane protégée afin de ne pas rayer le polycarbonate.
- Retirer les films de protection des polycarbonates.
- Appliquer de la feutrine autocollante sur les surfaces en contact des éléments intérieurs et extérieurs (barre longue, barre courte, maison)
- Faire des essais préalables pour avoir les forces d'aimantations adéquates.
- Effectuer le montage polycarbonate + joint + cadre PVC + joint + polycarbonate à la main en serrant uniformément tous les boulons.
- Les bouchons coniques servant au remplissage/vidange, doivent être insérés à une profondeur d'environ 8mm.

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SIEMENS

THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE
TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE

FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	TITLE	
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)	Plan d'ensemble	
CHECKED BY			
APPROVED BY			

SIZE	DRG NO.	SHEET REV
A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
SCALE 1:5		SHEET 1 OF 9

A3

Quantité : 1
Matière: PVC

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SIEMENS		THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE		
FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	TITLE		
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)	Détail Cadre		
CHECKED BY				
APPROVED BY		SIZE	DRG NO.	SHEET REV
		A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
		SCALE 1:5	SHEET 2 OF 9	

Quantité : 2
 Matière: Néoprène cellulaire

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SIEMENS		THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE		
FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	Détail Joints		
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)			
CHECKED BY				
APPROVED BY		SIZE	DRG NO.	SHEET REV
		A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
		SCALE 1:5	SHEET 3 OF 9	

Quantité : 2
Matière : Polycarbonate

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SIEMENS		THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE		
FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	TITLE		
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)	Détail Faces		
CHECKED BY				
APPROVED BY		SIZE	DRG NO.	SHEET REV
		A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
		SCALE 1:5		SHEET 4 OF 9

Logements pour disque magnétique caoutchouté Ø22mm

SECTION B-B

Quantité : 2
Matière : PVC

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SIEMENS		THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE		
FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	TITLE Détail Barre longue		
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)			
CHECKED BY				
APPROVED BY		SIZE	DRG NO.	SHEET REV
		A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
		SCALE 1:1	SHEET 5 OF 9	

Logements pour disque magnétique caoutchouté Ø22mm

SECTION A-A

Quantité : 2
Matière : PVC

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SIEMENS		THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE		
FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	TITLE Détail Barre courte		
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)			
CHECKED BY		SIZE DRG NO.		SHEET REV
APPROVED BY		A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
		SCALE 1:1	SHEET 6 OF 9	

SECTION C-C

Quantité : 1
Matière: PVC

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SIEMENS		THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE		
FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	TITLE Détail Maison		
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)			
CHECKED BY		SIZE DRG NO.		SHEET REV
APPROVED BY		A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
		SCALE 1:1	SHEET 7 OF 9	

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

Quantité : 2
Matière: PVC

SIEMENS		THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE		
FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	Détail Socle		
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)			
CHECKED BY				
APPROVED BY		SIZE	DRG NO.	SHEET REV
		A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
		SCALE 1:2	SHEET 8 OF 9	

Quantité : 1
 Matière : PVC

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SIEMENS		THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN PRODUCED USING AN EXAMPLE TEMPLATE PROVIDED BY SIEMENS PLM SOFTWARE		
FIRST ISSUED	26/10/2023	TITLE Détail Crémaillère		
DRAWN BY	BARRON (IMFT)			
CHECKED BY				
APPROVED BY		SIZE	DRG NO.	SHEET REV
		A3	demonstrateur_dwg	A
		SCALE 1:2	SHEET 9 OF 9	